

DIMENSION OF AUTONOMOUS LEARNING AND LEVEL OF LEARNER AUTONOMY CORRELATES OF ENGLISH LANGUAGE PROFICIENCY

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ABSTRACT

The autonomy among learners becomes particularly crucial in today's learning as the new normal situation transforms the education in the Philippines. This study aimed to determine the perception of the students on the dimension of autonomous learning and their perceived level of autonomy on their teacher's aims and requirements, establishing study goals and plan, learning strategy's implementation, ability to monitor the usage of learning strategies and English learning process. This study also measured the English language proficiency of the students. Moreover, this study attempted to correlate the perception of the students' dimension of autonomous learning and the level of learner autonomy to their English language proficiency in the subcomponents such as grammar, vocabulary, and reading comprehension. The study utilized a descriptive and correlational research design specifically quantitative methods with the survey questionnaires and proficiency test to gather data among FAITH Fidelis Senior high school students from Darasa, Tanauan Batangas. The study revealed that there is a significant relationship between the dimension of autonomous learning as to responsibility and English language proficiency. The result indicates that students still rely the responsibility on their teacher when learning grammar and vocabulary in English. Also, it was found out that the perceived level of learner autonomy and English language proficiency has no significant relationship. The results implies that respondents' perception on their level of autonomy is not an indicator of their success in English language proficiency.

Keywords: Autonomous Learning, Learner Autonomy, English language proficiency, Descriptive and correlational, Fidelis Senior Highschool